
WEB BASED LIBRARY SERVICES

Dr. Vidhya Sharad Modi

Librarian, Arts and Commerce College, Phondaghat.

Corresponding Author - Dr. Vidhya Sharad Modi

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Abstract:

Internet and the World Wide Web (WWW) are new media platforms that provide greater efficiency and speed to the delivery of information than anything else that is available today. A library has been able to store, retrieve, and communicate information in a more efficient and effective manner by using the Internet and web technology. With more and more libraries aiming to provide their services in a digital environment, the ease of access to remote library resources is making it more realistic and attractive for users to use electronic information sources as a means of providing their services. Web-based services are examined in this paper, as well as the reasons they are so popular. There have been several web resources highlighted. A discussion of the future and conclusion was also conducted at the end of the paper.

Keywords: *Web Based Services, Need & Future of Web Services.*

Introduction:

The advent of the Internet, and specifically the World Wide Web, which is one of its major services, has changed the way people communicate, learn, teach, do business, find employment, educate and seek healthcare. The 21st century publishing and information delivery system has been significantly affected by it. Libraries too have been transformed by applications of internet and web technologies, which have changed how information is provided to users and how they operate. In order to promote education and research, libraries play a vital role. In addition to having access to information sources and databases located all over the world, this technology enabled users to access various sources of information. The library is now accessible from anywhere at any time. Physical library visits are not required, nor is there a

time limit. The availability of computer content on desktops has been made possible by technology and web-based services. There are several different kinds of software available to provide web-based library services. The library portal is one type of software that facilitates access to web-based library resources. A web-based library portal provides access to the library's web-based resources, which are provided primarily through library portals. A library's multiple databases can be accessed through it, providing integrated access to metadata. Users can customize their info resources by choosing and viewing information they find useful in person on a single webpage that gathers a variety of useful information resources.

World Wide Web:

As part of the Internet, you can access the World Wide Web. An internet

browser is a method of accessing web pages containing integrated information via an internet connection. In the World Wide Web, interlinked documents are accessible locally and remotely through a network of internet servers. The Internet provides computer users with a wide range of data on a large number of subjects, through a worldwide network of connected machine-readable text files. There are several ways to provide information, including text, hypertext, pictures, sounds, and using net news groups. Internet Explorer, Firefox, etc., are client programs required to access web-based information. The Internet transmits data using the http protocol language. Links to other web pages can be found on every web page on the web. Hypertext is a method of linking words and information on a page by highlighting one or more of the items on the page.

Web Based Library Services:

In terms of World Wide Web, Internet, and online, WEB is the most popular term. There are several components to the communication method, such as the Internet and the WWW. Links to other pages will be included in every page, in addition to data. Among the pages are different words or sequences of words highlighted, along with other information related to them. Hypertext is a service that links one item with another and provides a link between them. In order to display a new page, the browser connects to the web server at the location of the link, requests the new page, and then displays it. The WWW could represent an intermediate type between recorded and unrecorded communication and knowledge transfer. In the early stages of the development of this medium, its dynamics have not been fully defined. Today, the web is the perfect

medium for providing information because of the tremendous increase of information and the changes in user behaviour. We will fancy the type of internet there are some common facilities.

Need of Web Based Library Service:

There are many qualities that are required of library services on the internet, just as there are in traditional references: accuracy, promptness, courtesy, and knowledge about the information that is required. In addition to providing convenience, it saves users time and travel costs and helps them answer reference questions in their own time. As a result, these services can be provided 24 hours a day, 7 days a week, without being restricted by traditional opening hours. Using electronic library services may have some disadvantages, such as not having the option of face-to-face contact, but there are many advantages as well, the greatest of which is that many more people are able to benefit.

Web Based Library Service:

Libraries with digital services manage and develop their websites, electronic resources, and staff. A service that allows users to access information electronically, such as through email or web forms, can be broadly defined as 'an electronic means of accessing information'.

Library Webpage:

As a gateway to finding information about a library, library webpages function as gateways to locating information about libraries. In addition to providing access to the metadata of a library's various databases, e-journals, and library catalogues, it also provides detailed information about a library by integrating

the metadata of these sources. In addition, it provides access to all computer-based services, such as library collection, library timing, library working hours, list of subscribed online journals, CAS/SDI/Reference services, popular documents that are circulated, reserved, and received feedback from users, etc. Among the services a library offers is the time and location of its collection. A library webpage provides libraries with an easy way to advertise their services and facilities globally.

Web OPAC:

A Web OPAC is a library catalogue that can be accessed online. The URL of Web OPAC will enable users to access the desired information anywhere in the world, at any time. A user can access bibliographic information about holdings in a particular library's collection by using this tool. It is organized based on the subject content that is given a call number for library books. Web OPAC offers a variety of services including library catalogues, search facilities for whole databases, and restricted access for groups of users and guests.

Bulletin Board:

Bulletin boards are electronic communication forums where people post articles and messages about a common topic. Users can leave or retrieve messages by calling in. Bulletin boards can be used to send messages to all members or to specific members. In several libraries, bulletin boards are used as an integral part of their internet-based library services. As an interactive interface for suggestions on library activities and services, bulletin boards can also be used as a bulletin board. In addition, it can be used as a means of disseminating library services.

Access to Database:

There are several publishers today that provide native access to their databases via web-based, network-based solutions. Among the most popular databases are Silver Platter, Cambridge Scientific Abstracts, and Institute for Scientific Information. Publishers of journals have also begun offering electronic versions of their journals, such as Elsevier. It is possible for large research and development libraries to make use of these developments and provide their users with access to key databases and electronic publications through desktop computers. Libraries have an assortment of ROM databases installed on their CD server/towers in addition to the outwardly purchased databases. Databases are delivered over the internet by companies such as Dialog, Lexis-Nexis, and ERIC. In this way, libraries that subscribe to these databases are now able to access them over the Internet.

Electronic Selective Dissemination of information:

Using an electronic SDI service, faculty members can receive current information of interest directly to their desktops. It is a service that searches monthly the Research Interest Profiles (RIPs) on the latest updates of EDBs in a batch mode and emails the results to faculty members. In addition to providing current awareness, this service has also had a significant impact on acquiring information sources, sharing resources, and acquiring reprints from the library. By hyper-navigating the active link, library users can trace the different tasks followed to provide E-SDI services on the web through the existing library environment. A general definition of E-SDI is that it involves matching the user's profile to the

material, notifying the user of feedback he or she gives, and modifying the user's profile accordingly. The next few links outline the process of delivering the output, an answer to frequently asked questions, feedback from users, statistical information about the service, and a figurative representation of the process.

Ask-A-Librarian:

Web-based Ask-A-Librarian services are question and answer services. Users may submit questions through the service's website or via an e-mail address. An individual expert answers the query once the query has been read by a service, providing actual information or a list of resources to answer the query. Users can either receive responses by email or by browsing the internet so they can access them after a certain period of time.

Web Based User Education:

Guides and teaching tools may be found all over the web due to the ease of updating, accessing, and printing them. Users benefit from a high degree of interactivity and flexibility when educating themselves on the web. Using web-based user education, library websites will impart instruction to users in the following areas:

- Basic library skills coupled with a glossary of library terms;
- Locate books, magazines, and other library materials using Library OPAC/Web OPAC;
- A description of how to search fixed storage databases, online databases, and other alternative electronic resources; and
- Searching internet resources through search engines and using Boolean operators are all included in the subject search training.

News Group:

These are online discussion groups covering a wide variety of topics. In order to view and post messages in newsgroups, you must use a program called a newsreader. With newsgroups, readers can choose the topics they want to discuss instead of being limited to mail lists or chat rooms. Scientists and professionals can benefit greatly from them. In order to enhance the knowledge base of organizations, special libraries should provide opportunities for users to participate in newsgroups. Staff members can post messages in the appropriate newsgroup to discuss library issues, new technologies adopted in libraries, and so on.

Great Reader's Advisory Services Found on the Web:

The reader's advisory service is closely related to reference services, but is often neglected in libraries due to a lack of staff. Reader's advisory librarians are rewarded when patrons return books, just as reference librarians gain great satisfaction from answering reference questions. The provision of reference services does not have to be confined to in-house operations. It is possible to offer this service on the library's website. New fiction, mysteries, nonfiction, etc., are all recommended and reviewed by the staff member. An online form allows readers to submit their own book reviews for publication on the site, and a search function allows visitors to find book reviews of specific titles. Links to web sites of interest to readers can be found as well as information on local book talks and book clubs.

Virtual Library Tours:

Virtual library guides can be found on the websites of libraries, providing information about the collections, services, and infrastructure available in the libraries. In order to present a tour of the library, maps and floor plans, departmental maps, and photographic views are used together with maps and floor plans. On main campus Web sites, virtual library tours are beginning to replace image maps with new technologies such as QuickTime movies.

Real Time Services:

The live reference service is an exciting way that libraries are offering digital reference services more and more nowadays. Using these services, users will be able to interact with a real, live reference librarian at any time, from anywhere in the world, which is an interactive, real-time service that allows them to talk to a librarian in real-time. The librarian can collaborate with the user using chat technology, and unlike with email reference, he or she can ask the user for clarification or elaboration before answering the question. Users can receive immediate feedback from the librarian on how they feel their question has been answered to their satisfaction based on Internet searches and websites pushed onto their browsers.

Gateways:

The term gateway refers to a facility that facilitates access to network-based resources in a specific field. An enhanced service is provided through a web-based interface that provides search facilities and indexes of resources. Hand cataloguing is done for information provided by gateways. A wide range of subjects are covered by subject gateways, but some areas, such as music and religion,

are currently unassigned. The following are some well-known gateways:

- IPL (Internet Public Library),
- BUBL (Built Board for Libraries),
- NISS (National Information Services and Systems),

Electronic Journals:

The collection of electronic journals in a library that provides web-based services makes up a large part of its collection. There are a large number of journals available electronically today - some of them are full text while others contain only the name and abstract of the journal. An advantage of electronic journals is their constant updating and accessibility, but a disadvantage is that copyright laws are easily broken. There are many formats available, including bitmaps, PostScript, PDF, ASCII, SGML and HTML. CD Rom, emails, and web pages may be used to deliver library services to users. There are some international societies and associations that provide access to all their publications through their own digital libraries. Subscribers can access services offered by societies or associations.

The Future of Web Based Services:

Web services for libraries will continue to grow, with more journals and indexes offering full-text content. Those without full-text content will link to external resources. Through cataloguing, databases, or vendors, full-text periodicals will be more easily accessible via bibliographic search. More Web forms will be available for the user to provide feedback, and perhaps a virtual librarian will be available to interact with the user in real-time chats or video conferencing sessions. There is an incentive to deliver more documents through distance

education or to users, to save on interlibrary loans, and to provide convenience to users. It will be popular to purchase information resources through creative consortia. Modules and tutorials designed for user education, particularly to support independent exploration of library and Web resources. In order to prevent Word users from saving print documents as XML, someone has to figure out how to make them think in terms of the Web and not print space when saving print documents. The use of XML as a method of controlling page appearance and behaviour will be embraced by all, but it will take some time for people to figure out how to utilize it and we will have to keep an eye on new trends that will emerge.

Conclusion:

Libraries have the primary function of providing quality information services to their users to satisfy their needs with the right information at the right time. There is a trend toward web-based library services. The main purpose of our library remains the same regardless of how we transfer service, namely helping users find, evaluate, and use information effectively. A librarian may be able to serve their techno savvy users better with web-based library services, helping meet these challenges. There is an important role for

librarians to play in the learning community, both as collaborators and coaches, in order to help students find the information they need, teach them how to conduct a successful search, and help them judge the quality and usefulness of the information that they come across.

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